

A STUDY TO UNVEIL ANEMIA PATTERN IN CKD-5D; A THOROUGH EXAMINATION OF PATIENTS UNDERGOING MAINTAINANCE HEMODIALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a significant health concern with high mortality, and anemia is a frequent and serious complication that can worsen disease outcomes. Effective management of anemia, especially in patients undergoing maintenance haemodialysis (HD), is crucial for improving clinical outcomes. This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence of anemia in CKD patients on maintenance HD, assess current diagnostic and management practices, and explore the impact of patient compliance on treatment outcomes.

A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 150 HD patients in Bengaluru. Data were collected on anemia prevalence, diagnostic methods, treatment practices, and patient awareness and adherence. Patients received counseling to promote regular monitoring and medication adherence. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics.

The study found that anemia affected 82% of the participants, with a higher prevalence among older individuals. Haemoglobin levels were commonly monitored monthly or bi-monthly. Erythropoietin and iron injections were the most frequently used treatments. However, the study revealed poor patient awareness and compliance: 64% were unaware of anemia as a CKD complication, 82% did not undergo regular testing, 50% lacked knowledge about anemia management, and 64% were non-adherent to therapy. Counseling significantly improved adherence, with a 63.7% improvement noted.

In conclusion, anemia is highly prevalent among CKD patients on HD, with inadequate patient education and poor adherence to treatment being major challenges. The findings underscore the need for enhanced patient education, better diagnostic follow-ups, and accessible treatment strategies to manage anemia effectively in this vulnerable population.

KEYWORDS: Anemia, Chronic kidney diseases, Medication adherence, Haemodialysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Anemia in Chronic Kidney Disease: Pathophysiology, Diagnosis, and Management

Anemia is a clinical condition characterized by a reduction in the number of red blood cells (RBCs) or haemoglobin, the iron-containing protein essential for transporting oxygen from the lungs to body tissues and organs. Insufficient haemoglobin levels result in impaired oxygen delivery, affecting the normal function of vital organs such as the heart and brain. Globally, anemia affects approximately 1.74 billion individuals, accounting for 22.8% of the world's population. In the context of chronic kidney disease (CKD), anemia often develops insidiously and may remain asymptomatic in its early stages.

The clinical manifestations of anemia include fatigue, weakness, pallor or yellowish skin, shortness of breath, irregular heartbeats, dizziness, chest discomfort, cold extremities, easy bruising, and headaches. In many cases, anemia is incidentally discovered during investigations for other underlying conditions.

Anemia is broadly categorized based on red blood cell size into microcytic, normocytic, and macrocytic types. Microcytic anemia, characterized by smaller-than-normal RBCs, is commonly caused by iron deficiency, sideroblastic anemia, thalassemia, or lead poisoning. Management is etiology-specific and may include iron supplementation, vitamin B6 therapy, blood transfusions, or bone marrow transplantation in severe cases. Normocytic anemia presents with normal-sized RBCs but reduced in number and is often associated with chronic illnesses such as autoimmune disorders, infections, malignancies, or bone marrow pathologies. It may also result from blood loss or haemolysis, with treatment directed at the underlying condition. Macrocytic anemia features enlarged RBCs and is sub-classified into megaloblastic and non-megaloblastic types. Megaloblastic anemia results from vitamin B12 or folate deficiency and is treated with appropriate

supplementation. Pernicious anemia, a form of megaloblastic anemia, involves impaired B12 absorption and may necessitate lifelong parenteral B12 therapy. Non-megaloblastic macrocytic anemia may be attributed to hypothyroidism, chronic alcohol use, liver disease, or genetic disorders such as hereditary spherocytosis.

The pathophysiology of anemia involves decreased RBC production (due to nutritional deficiencies or bone marrow failure), increased RBC destruction (as seen in haemolytic anaemias), acute or chronic blood loss, and defective RBC function due to structural abnormalities or marrow infiltration by malignancies such as leukaemia. Diagnosis typically begins with a complete blood count (CBC), assessing haemoglobin, haematocrit, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), and red cell distribution width (RDW). Further investigations may include iron studies (serum iron, ferritin, total iron-binding capacity, and transferrin saturation), vitamin B12 and folate levels, peripheral blood smear, and bone marrow biopsy when indicated.

If left untreated, anemia can lead to serious complications such as cardiac murmurs, left ventricular hypertrophy, and congestive heart failure due to increased cardiac workload. In pregnancy, untreated anemia can contribute to adverse outcomes including preterm delivery and low birth weight. Timely diagnosis and targeted treatment are essential to prevent complications and improve patient outcomes¹.

Chronic Kidney Disease and Anemia

Chronic kidney disease is a progressive condition characterized by a sustained decline in kidney function, leading to impaired waste excretion and homeostatic imbalance. It is diagnosed when kidney damage persists for ≥ 3 months or when the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) falls below 60 mL/min/1.73 m², irrespective of structural abnormalities. According to the 2012 KDIGO guidelines, CKD is classified into six stages (G1–G5) based on GFR, with G3 further divided into G3a and G3b. CKD affects over 700 million people worldwide, with a global prevalence exceeding 10%. The disease is often underdiagnosed in early stages, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where awareness and screening remain limited.

Anemia is a prevalent complication of CKD and increases in frequency with advancing disease—from 8.4% in Stage 1 to over 53% in Stage 5. It is more common among individuals aged over 60 years. CKD is usually asymptomatic early on, but patients may later experience symptoms such as fatigue, pruritus, weight loss, swelling, frequent urination (often with a foul odor), and cognitive difficulties. Major risk factors for CKD include diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, obesity, aging, family history, prior kidney injury, smoking, autoimmune disorders, infections, nephrolithiasis, and congenital anomalies.

Diagnosis of CKD involves a thorough clinical history, physical examination, blood and urine tests, imaging studies, and, if necessary, kidney biopsy. Management focuses on slowing disease progression and mitigating complications through blood pressure control (e.g., with ACE inhibitors or ARBs), glycaemic management in diabetes, and dietary modifications such as protein, sodium, and potassium restriction. Anemia is treated using iron supplementation and erythropoiesis-stimulating agents (ESAs). Additional complications such as mineral bone disorders are managed with phosphate binders, vitamin D analogues, and calcium supplementation. Fluid overload may necessitate diuretics or dialysis. In end-stage renal disease (ESRD), renal replacement therapy via dialysis or transplantation becomes necessary. Early detection and intervention are crucial for optimizing patient outcomes².

Dialysis and Anemia Management

Dialysis is a life-sustaining therapy for patients with ESRD, characterized by $<15\%$ of normal kidney function. It substitutes for renal excretion by removing toxins and excess fluids from the blood. Two primary dialysis modalities exist: peritoneal dialysis (PD), which uses the peritoneum as a filter and can be performed manually (CAPD) or via automated devices; and haemodialysis (HD), which involves extracorporeal filtration using a dialyzer and vascular access (e.g., arteriovenous fistula or graft).

Renal anemia is a common complication in dialysis patients, primarily due to reduced erythropoietin (EPO) synthesis by the failing kidneys. Other contributors include iron deficiency (from dietary restrictions or blood loss), reduced RBC lifespan, frequent phlebotomy, and eryptosis—a programmed form of RBC death

exacerbated by hypoxia and oxidative stress during dialysis. Management includes ESA therapy and iron supplementation, though treatment resistance may occur²⁻⁵.

Role of Erythropoietin and Iron in Erythropoiesis

Erythropoietin, mainly produced by peritubular interstitial cells of the kidney under hypoxic conditions, is critical for terminal erythroid maturation. It acts on burst-forming unit-erythroid (BFU-E) and colony-forming unit-erythroid (CFU-E) progenitors, which are dependent on EPO for differentiation.

Iron metabolism is essential to erythropoiesis and involves intestinal absorption, cellular storage (via ferritin), and systemic transport (via transferrin). Dietary ferric iron (Fe^{3+}) is reduced to ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}) for absorption via divalent metal transporter 1 (DMT1), followed by export through ferroprotein. Hepcidin, a liver-derived peptide, is the master regulator of systemic iron homeostasis. It inhibits ferroprotein activity, decreasing iron availability during inflammation or iron overload⁴.

Anemia in CKD: Diagnosis and Therapeutic Strategies

CKD-related anemia is multifactorial, with EPO deficiency as the primary etiology. Additional mechanisms include uremic inhibitors of erythropoiesis, iron dysregulation, and functional iron deficiency due to elevated hepcidin levels. Diagnosis relies on clinical evaluation and laboratory assessments, including haemoglobin, ferritin, transferrin saturation (TSAT), and vitamin B12 and folate levels, especially in cases of macrocytic anemia.

Treatment prioritizes correction of iron deficiency before initiating ESA therapy. Intravenous iron, particularly iron sucrose, is preferred due to superior efficacy and safety. ESAs such as recombinant human EPO and long-acting continuous erythropoietin receptor activators (CERA) are used to raise haemoglobin levels and improve quality of life. Vitamin supplementation (B12, folate, B6) is also recommended to counteract dialysis-related losses and dietary limitations. Hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF) stabilizers, a novel therapeutic class, enhance endogenous EPO synthesis and represent a promising alternative to traditional ESA therapy⁶⁻⁷.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study is a prospective observational study conducted at the Department of Nephrology (Dialysis Unit) of Sagar Hospital Care Hospital, Bengaluru, over a six-month duration.

A total of 150 dialysis patients from the dialysis unit of Sagar Hospital who met the study criteria were enrolled in the study.

1.1. Study Material

- Self-designed data collection form
- Questionnaire
- Patient information sheet
- Patient consent form
- Patient information leaflet

1.2. Ethical Approval:

Ethical committee clearance has been obtained by the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC) of Sagar Hospital, Bengaluru 560041

1.3. Study Criteria:

1.3.1. Inclusion criteria:

- Patients aged 18 years or above will be included.

- Patients diagnosed with CKD on Maintenance Haemodialysis.
- Patients receiving care at hospital and consenting to the study.

1.3.2. Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who do not give consent for the study are excluded.
- Patient having Psychiatric Disorder are excluded.
- Patients with primary diagnosis of acute kidney injury will be excluded.

1.4. Study Procedure

1.4.1. Method of data collection:

A comprehensive six-month prospective cross-sectional study was conducted in the Nephrology department of Tertiary Care Hospital-Bengaluru. Eligible patients meeting specific criteria will be enrolled, and data was meticulously gathered from patient case notes, laboratory reports, treatment charts, and direct patient interactions. Patient demographics, medication history, social history, and family history will be extracted from case notes, while laboratory data encompassing CBC test, Iron profile test, B12, Folic acid, GFR, and Serum Creatinine was sourced from lab reports. The study will delve into drug-related information obtained from treatment charts, with particular attention to patients' interactions to discern medication compliance and explore factors such as cost, side effects, and lack of information. All collected information will be meticulously documented in a tailored data collection form titled 'A study on the prevalence of Anemia in Chronic Kidney Diseases-Stage 5 on maintenance haemodialysis.' Follow-ups will also be diligently recorded for comprehensive analysis and patients were counselled to understand their diseases condition, importance of regular check-ups, and adherence to medication to uplift their health-related quality of life.

1.4.2. Data analysis:

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 25.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp. Descriptive statistics with frequency, mean, and standard deviation were computed. Normality of the data was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Inferential statistics, like the Mann-Whitney test, were used to check the difference between the groups. The chi-square test was used to find out differences between proportions. The significance of the level adopted was 5%.

2. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to age [N=150]

AGE	Frequency (no.)	Percentage (%)
20-40	18	12
40-60	49	32.7
Above 60	83	55.3
Total	150	100

Table no.1 Shows the frequency and percentage of age group included in this study with total mean Mean±SD years, Range: 27-87 years, A total of 150 patients were enrolled among which the majority 55.3% (83) were above 60 years followed by 32.7% (49) were in between the age of 40-60 years and 12% (18) were aged between 20-40 years, and below figure represents the same.

Table No. 2: Distribution of patients according to gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	95	63.3
Female	55	36.7
Total	150	100

Table no.2 shows frequency and percentage of male and female patients included in the study, A total of 150 patients were enrolled among which male were in the majority, being 63.3% (95) and 36.7% (55) were females.

Table no. 3: Distribution of patients according to social history

Social history	Frequency	Percentage
Government scheme	31	20.7
Private insurance	68	45.3
Self-cost bearer	51	34
Total	150	100

Table no.3 shows the frequency and percentage of social history [cost management] of the patient included in the study, A total of 150 patients were enrolled in the study among which majority being 45.3% (68) patients were dependent on private insurance, followed by 34% (51) being self-bearer and 20.7% (31) being dependent on government scheme.

Table no. 4: Distribution of patients according to medication history [N=150]

Medication History	Frequency	Percentage
Not known	93	62.0
Iron supplement	31	20.7
Erythropoietin	21	14.0
Iron injection with Erythropoietin	05	3.3
Total	150	100

Table no. 4 shows the frequency and percentage of medication history of the patients included in the study, A total of 150 patients were enrolled in the study among which majority 62% (93) not knowing, 20.7% (31) were on iron injection ,14% (21) were on erythropoietin injection and 3.3% (5).

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Table no. 5: Distribution of patients according to Diabetes [N=150]

Diabetes	Frequency	Percentage
No	45	30.0
Yes	105	70.0
Total	150	100

Table no.5 shows the frequency and percentage of the patients included in the study having diabetes, among total participant 70% (105) were having diabetes and 30% (45) were not having.

Table no. 6: Distribution of patients according to blood transfusion[N=150]

Blood transfusion	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	90	60
No	60	40
Total	150	100

frequency and percentage of blood transfusion of the patients included in the study, A total of 150 participants were enrolled in the study among which 60% (90) underwent blood transfusion and 40% (60) did not.

Table no. 7: Distribution of patients according to hypertension [N=150]

Hypertension	Frequency	Percentage
No	68	45.3
Yes	82	54.7
Total	150	100

Table no.7 shows the frequency and percentage of the patients having Hypertension included in the study, among total participant 54.7% (82) were having hypertension and 45.3% (68) were not having.

Table No. 8: Changes in parameters before and after treatment

Parameters	Before (Mean±SD)	After (Mean±SD)
Hb	10.48±1.87	10.97±1.68
PCV	35.87±10.05	37.57±10.16
MCV	85.04±11.03	85.26±26
MCH	28.60±2.80	28.94±2.68
MCHC	32.09±2.50	32.40±3.05
S. Iron	57.58±33.10	60.76±33.74
Transferrin	23.09±10.55	30.67±39.99
Ferritin	165.41±287.50	223.67±374.05
Vit B12	530.81±514.25	552.62±267.76
Folic acid	7.91±8.63	8.69±8.52
Calcium	8.86±4.64	9.40±5.23
S. albumin	3.96±7.39	3.77±3.13

Table no. 8 shows that treatment resulted in notable improvements in various hematological and biochemical parameters. Hemoglobin (Hb) levels increased from 10.48±1.87 g/dL to 10.97±1.68 g/dL, indicating a positive response in anemia management. Correspondingly, packed cell volume (PCV) rose from 35.87±10.05% to 37.57±10.16%. Other red blood cell indices showed minor changes, with mean corpuscular volume (MCV) and mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) slightly increasing to 85.26±26 and 28.94±2.68, respectively. The mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) also improved from 32.09±2.50% to 32.40±3.05%. Biochemical analyses revealed an increase in serum iron from 57.58±33.10 µg/dL to 60.76±33.74 µg/dL, along with a significant rise in transferrin from 23.09±10.55 mg/dL to 30.67±39.99 mg/dL and ferritin levels from 165.41±287.50 ng/mL to 223.67±374.05 ng/mL, suggesting enhanced iron status. Vitamin B12 levels also showed a minor increase from 530.81±514.25 pg/mL to 552.62±267.76 pg/mL, and folic acid levels rose from 7.91±8.63

ng/mL to 8.69 ± 8.52 ng/ml. Other parameters, including calcium and serum albumin, demonstrated notable changes, with calcium increasing from 8.86 ± 4.64 mg/dL to 9.40 ± 5.23 mg/dL, while serum albumin slightly decreased from 3.96 ± 7.39 g/dL to 3.77 ± 3.13 g/dL.

Table 9: Prevalence of anemia among study subjects [N=150]

Anemia		Frequency	Percentage
Before	Present	123	82
	Absent	27	18
Total		150	100
After	Present	108	72
	Absent	42	28
Total		150	100

Table no. 9 shows the frequency and percentage of prevalence of anemia included in the study, the study enrolled total of 150 patients among which 82% (123) were having anemia while 18% were not anemic after the adherence to medication prevalence of anemia decreased to 72% (108).

Table no. 10: Distribution of patients with response to questionnaire on Knowledge[N=150]

Questions	No		Yes	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Do you know that anemia is associated with chronic kidney disease	87	58.0	63	42.0
Are you aware of the complications of anemia	76	50.7	74	49.3
Are you doing all the test such as CBC count, iron profile, and other tests	123	82.0	27	18.0
Have you been informed about the need for medications for anemia while on hemodialysis	75	50.0	75	50.0
Is your anemia being treated	96	64.0	54	36.0

Table no. 10 shows the total number of patients and percentages of patients responses of questions, A total of 150 patients were enrolled in the study among which 58%(87) of the patient were unaware of the anemia being complication of CKD,50.7%(76) of total participants were not aware of its complications, 82%(123) skipping their monthly tests, 54%(96) unaware of their treatment and 50%(75) lacking information regarding treatment.

Table no. 11: Reason for non-adherence among study subjects [N=150]

Reason	Frequency	Percentage
Cost	08	17.4
Lack of information	30	65.2
Adverse effect	01	2.2
No reason	07	15.2

Table no. 11 shows the frequency and percentage of reason for non-adherence included in the study, among study participants 65.2% (30) were non-adherent due to lack of information, 17.4(08) were not adherent due to cost, 15.2% (07) non-adherent without any reason and 2.2% (01) were non adherent due to adverse effects.

Table no. 12: Impact of adherence [N=150]

Impact of adherence	Frequency	Percentage
Improvement	86	67.7
No improvement	41	32.3

Table no.12 shows the frequency and percentages of impact of adherence, among total 150 enrolled participants 67.7% (86) showed improvement in condition.

Table 13: Association between anemia and age [N=150]

Anemia	Age (years)						<i>p</i> value *
	20-40		40-60		>60		
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Absent	07	5.6	10	8.1	10	8.1	0.02
Present	11	8.9	39	31.7	73	59	

*Chi-square test

Table no.13 shows the association between anemia and age, among prevalent anemia patient 59% (73) patient was aged above 60 years, 31.7% (39) patients were between age of 40-60 and 8.9% (11) patients were between age of 20-40 .

Table No. 14: Association between anemia and duration of dialysis

Duration of dialysis (years)	Anemia			
	Present		Absent	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 year	20	16.2	5	18.5
1-2 years	39	31.7	14	51.8
2-3 years	22	17.8	4	14.8
More than 3 years	42	34.1	4	14.8
Total	123	100	27	100

Table no.14 shows the association between anemia and duration of dialysis, among prevalent anemia patient. The majority of patients with anemia have been on dialysis for more than 3 years (34.1%) or 1-2 years (31.7%), while fewer patients with anemia have been on dialysis for less than 1 year (16.2%) or 2-3 years (17.8%).

Table NO.15: Association between frequency of Maintenance haemodialysis and anemia [N=150]

Frequency of MHD	Anemia			
	Present		Absent	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
2 times a week	49	39.9	10	37
3 times a week	74	60.1	17	63
Total	123	100	27	100

Table no.15 shows the association between anemia and frequency of hemodialysis, among prevalent anemia patient, the majority of patients undergoing MHD 3 times a week (60.1%) are having anemia compared to a smaller percentage who undergo MHD 2 times a week (39.9%).

DICUSSION

Our study showed age distribution is consistent with previous research on the prevalence of anemia in older adults. Anemia is a common, multifactorial condition among older adults, with a prevalence that rises with age and surpasses 20% in those 85 years of age and older, according to a study by Stauder and Thein (2014). Our results support this pattern, highlighting the increased vulnerability of older adults to anemia as a result of age-related physiological changes and comorbidities, as well as the important influence of financial backgrounds on access to healthcare. Although most patients have private insurance, the use of government programs and self-funding suggests possible inequalities. Achieving equitable access to healthcare requires addressing these disparities through inclusive policies and enhanced coverage.¹¹

In this study, we assessed the prevalence of anemia among 150 patients, revealing that initially, 82% (123 patients) were diagnosed with anemia, while only 18% (27 patients) were not. Following treatment adherence, the prevalence of anemia decreased to 72% (108 patients), indicating a significant improvement due to the therapeutic interventions implemented. These results emphasize the critical role of effective treatment in managing anemia, particularly among vulnerable populations. When comparing these findings with the study by Zaawari et al. (2022) on the prevalence of anemia among chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients in India, it is evident that anemia is a common complication in both studies. Zaawari et al. reported that 73% CKD patients experience anemia, often due to factors like impaired erythropoiesis and increased inflammation. The high initial prevalence of anemia in our study (82%) resonates with their findings, which underscore the importance of addressing anemia in patients with chronic conditions.¹²

A substantial majority, 62.0% (93 patients), reported an unknown medication history, indicating a lack of documentation or awareness regarding their previous treatments. Among those with known medication histories, 20.7% (31 patients) were using iron supplements, while 14.0% (21 patients) received erythropoietin. A small fraction, 3.3% (5 patients), were on a combined regimen of iron injections and erythropoietin. These findings suggest significant gaps in medication awareness, which could impact treatment efficacy and patient outcomes.

Its effectiveness in treating anemia was demonstrated by the notable improvements in a number of hematological and biochemical parameters that occurred when 150 patients followed their prescribed course of treatment. These results are in line with those of Mohan et al. (2021), who looked at how nutritional supplements affected anemia patients. Our findings also show that supplementing with a combination of micronutrients has a beneficial effect on managing anemia. The observed improvements in hematological and biochemical parameters imply that the nutritional deficiencies linked to anemia are adequately addressed by the treatment regimen. Together with improvements in vitamin B12 and folic acid levels, the rise in iron status indicators suggests a thorough nutritional intervention. Our research offers proof that the treatment is effective in raising important nutritional and hematological indicators.¹³

The association between anemia and the duration of dialysis among 150 patients. The data indicate that a significant proportion of patients with anemia have been on dialysis for more

than 3 years (34.1%) and 1-2 years (31.7%). In contrast, only 16.2% of patients with anemia have been on dialysis for less than 1 year, and 17.8% have been on dialysis for 2-3 years. This distribution suggests that longer durations of dialysis correlate with a higher prevalence of anemia, highlighting the potential impact of chronic kidney disease management and the cumulative effects of dialysis on patient health. A study by Akizawa et al. (2011) found that patients on dialysis for longer periods were significantly more likely to develop anemia due to factors such as iron deficiency and reduced erythropoietin response.¹⁴

The association between the frequency of maintenance hemodialysis (MHD) and the presence of anemia among 150 patients. In this study examining the association between the frequency of maintenance hemodialysis (MHD) and anemia among 150 patients, it was found that a significant majority of those undergoing MHD three times a week (60.1%) experienced anemia, compared to 39.9% of patients receiving treatment twice a week. This trend suggests that more frequent dialysis may be linked to a higher prevalence of anemia, potentially due to factors such as increased blood loss during dialysis sessions, altered erythropoietin production, or iron deficiency. A study by Macdougall et al. (2015) highlighted that patients undergoing more frequent dialysis tend to have lower hemoglobin levels, thereby supporting the current study's results.¹⁵

According to the findings, 58.0% of dialysis patients knew that anemia and chronic kidney disease were related. A similar study by Soundarya and Sumit found that 50.7% of dialysis patients knew that anemia can lead to complications, while 59% were not aware that anemia and CKD are related. A sizable majority, 82.0% (123 patients), stated that they had undergone pertinent tests like iron profiles and CBC counts. On the other hand, 75 patients, or 50.0% of the total, reported being aware of the need for medication while receiving hemodialysis. Additionally, 96 patients, or 64.0% of the total, reported that their anemia was being treated, whereas 54 patients, or 36.0%, did not. These results show that patients' awareness and treatment adherence vary, highlighting the need for better patient education and management techniques in this demographic.¹⁶

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the high burden of anemia among chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients undergoing maintenance haemodialysis, with a prevalence rate of 82% at baseline. It reveals critical gaps in patient awareness, education, and adherence to anemia management protocols. Despite the availability of effective treatments such as erythropoietin and iron supplementation, poor compliance, driven primarily by lack of information and financial barriers, undermines therapeutic outcomes. Encouragingly, targeted patient counseling significantly improved adherence and clinical parameters, including haemoglobin and nutritional markers. The findings emphasize the urgent need for integrated strategies focusing on patient education, regular monitoring, and accessible treatment to improve the quality of life and outcomes in this vulnerable population. Tailored interventions addressing age-related risks, dialysis frequency, and socioeconomic disparities are essential for more effective anemia management in CKD care.

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical committee clearance was obtained by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Sagar Hospital.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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